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Ontological Conception of Anekantavada: The Relativistic Interpretation of Jainism

Dr. Savithri.A¹

Abstract

The question regarding the ontology is always curious, whether it is real or unreal, one or many, spiritual or material, etc. The concept of Reality is one of the most important problems in Jaina Metaphysics. Based on their pluralistic nature, Jainism describes the epistemological, metaphysical doctrines as multidimensional. The theory of *Anekanta* deals with this multidimensional nature of reality. According to them the reality is always incomplete, as there are innumerable modes of existence, and each and every modes are independent of the other. The essential and the accidental qualities of an unchanging substance exists independently and makes the world possible only through the relativism. This paper is an attempt to analyze the relativistic interpretation of reality in the light of anekantavada, the pluralistic – multidimensional nature of truth

Keywords: *Anekanta*, Reality, Pluralism, Modes, Attributes, Change.

Introduction

The philosophical arguments about the origin, nature and development of reality are one of oldest issue in Indian tradition. When we look into the Indian philosophical traditions, we can see that they are deeply engaged with the problem of reality and there held that many metaphysical views were in constant argument with one another. In different contexts, metaphysics becomes cross-sectoral at various levels pertaining to the status of the concepts like, universals, God, soul, substances, time, change, permanence or impermanence, one and many, etc.... Some of the fundamental principles of Indian

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philosophy includes the unity of Absolute Reality and the problem of plurality, identity and difference, eternal calmness and eternal motion, transcendent knowledge as experience of Absolute Reality, the Self identical with or different from the Absolute, the nature of God, the nature of external reality, Being and non being, real and unreal nature of causality, etc...

As one of the ancient philosophical traditions of India Jainism upholds a variety of epistemological, logical, metaphysical and ontological doctrines based on their relative pluralism. Mc Evilly points out that the Jainas accepts three doctrines of relativity¹, namely, *anekantavada* or the theory of relative pluralism, *syadvada* or the theory of conditioned predication, and the *nayavada* or the theory of partial standpoints. These philosophical doctrines of Jainism made very significant contributions to the ancient Indian philosophy, especially in the areas of skepticism and relativity. The Jaina metaphysics is regarded as realistic and relativistic pluralism based on reality and relativity. Thus, the concept of reality according to Jainism proposes that, the reality cannot be the one and ultimate, it can have multi-dimensional form. In this sense, what is reality for one individual may not be the reality for others. The realistic and relativistic nature of Jaina tradition states that objects have infinite modes of existence and qualities. So, we cannot completely understand in all aspects and manifestations by the finite human experience and, no specific human view can claim to represent the absolute truth.

Anekantavada: Realistic and Relativistic Many-ness

The doctrine of *anekantavada*, or non-absolutism is one of the central concepts of Jainism which discusses the multidimensional nature of reality. According to the Jainists, the universe is an uncreated entity that has existed from the beginning of time and will continue to exist indefinitely. It is the fact that, for them, there was no beginning of the universe, and there will be no end of the universe. So that, the universe was not created at any point in time and will not be destroyed at any point in the future. In other words, the reality, according to them, is not concerned with any creator or destroyer of the world, and on the other hand, it concerned with the substances and modes through which the multitude of the

phenomenal world is existing. They generally did not discriminate between different types of substance, like, reality, existence, and so on but the very substance itself contains all these as one unity, and difference as well. The term 'Anekantavada' is referred as 'the doctrine of the many-ness of reality' or 'non-one-sidedness'. The word itself means that the reality is not one but many (*aneka*) and infinite, and it is commonly referred to as 'non-absolutism'. The theory firmly states that the ultimate truth and reality is complex and has many different aspects, and as a result, they cannot be completely grasped in all of their aspects and manifestations by human perception, which is limited. We, the finite being, can know only the partial truth of manifestations, and therefore, no single human viewpoint can be said to represent the absolute truth of a given situation. For example, one's experience of taste is always different from others and he/she tried to explain the truth of taste through language, it remains as incomplete. In the same way, according to Jaina thinkers, spiritual truths are complex, they have multiple aspects, language cannot express their plurality, yet through effort and appropriate karma they can be experienced.²

According to Jainism, all attempts to proclaim absolute truth are compared to the 'maxim of the blind men and elephant.' The following parable is used by the Jain authors to explain the multifold nature of truth:

"A group of blind men heard that a strange animal, called an elephant, had been brought to the town, but none of them were aware its shape and form. Out of curiosity, they said: "We must inspect and know it by touch of which we are capable." So, they sought it out, and when they found it, they groped about it. In the case of the first one person, whose hand landed on the trunk, said "This being is like a drain pipe." For another one whose hand reached its ear, it seemed like a kind of fan. As for another person, whose hand was upon its leg, said, "I perceive the shape of the elephant to be like a pillar." And in the case of the one who placed his hand upon its back said "Indeed, this elephant is like a throne." Now, each of these presented a true aspect when he related what he had gained from experiencing the elephant. None of them had strayed from the true description of the elephant. Yet they fell short of fathoming the true appearance of the elephant."³

The above-mentioned story of blind men and elephant tells us

that, how the people understand the reality in different ways that is, the experience of reality of a person is different from others. For example, one man felt the trunk, another the ears, and yet another the tail, etc...., and for them whatever they experience is real but, they experienced the different aspects of the same reality. Every blind man claimed to be able to explain the true appearance of the elephant, but due to their limited perspectives, they were only partially successful.

Analysis of substance and Modes

Now I would like to analyze the relativistic nature of reality through the substance (*dravya*) and modes (*pariyaya*), which are the fountain stone of the pluralistic philosophy of Jainism. A substance can be defined as something which possesses infinite qualities and modes of existence. It is very important to know the nature of substance to understand the correct characteristics of any entity. Umaswami in his *Tattvarthasutra* (5:29) substance is defined as: Sat dravyalakṣaṇam, means that, substance is the characteristics or indicator of reality (existent). B. K. Matilal rightly point out that, “the Jaina conception of existence (sat) was intimately related to their notion of substance. In fact, the Jainas redefined the notion of substance, in accordance with their anekanta principle, as a combination of the notion of *being* and *becoming*”.⁴ In every substance, there found two kinds of characters which are essential or permanent and changing or accidental. The Jaina thinkers calls an essential, unchanging, or permanent character of a thing as attribute (*guna*), and an accidental, changing character of a thing as modes (*pariyaya*), that is, the change occurring in an attribute or the constant ongoing modification of a substance is the mode. A substance, according to Jainism, has its unchanging essence and therefore it is permanent. But it has its changing modes and destruction as well. However, a substance is considered as permanent in the sense of its essence is characterized by indestructibility and continuity. It is subject to generation and destruction means that some new qualities may suffer the destruction. It is permanent in respect to its essential qualities and impermanent in respect to its changing modifications. The essential characters of a substance remain in the substance as long as the substance remains, as its permanent quality.

Without these qualities, the substance will cease to be what it is. For example, consciousness, is an essential character of the soul, and the accidental characters like, volitions, pleasure, pain, desires, etc., are changing, they will come and go, they succeed one another because they are the accidental qualities of the soul.

Reality, for the Jainas, is composed of both the permanency and the change. It is permanent when we viewed from the side of substance, on the other side it is many and changing when we view from the side of modes. When we recall the example given above, the elephant and the blind men, the substance, elephant, is real and one but the blind men are experiencing the different modes, as different parts of the elephant. Here, in Jainism, the reality or substance is distinguished from *dravya* as only one reality because they believe in the plurality of reality. *Dravya*, means that which exists and possesses three fundamental characteristics, namely, origin (*Utpada*), permanence (*Nithya*) and destruction (*Vyaya*). They maintain the identity of substance through its several qualities and modes. For them, in its reality, the *dravya* can neither be created nor destroyed, and has only permanent substantiality, but through its modes, it obtains the three-fold qualities of origin, permanence and, destruction. It is important to notice that the notion of continuity in the so-called triple character of a substance is not identical with the notion of permanence of the substance because the notion of continuity is essentially dependent on the origin and destruction. Kundakunda observes that, “There is no origin without destruction, nor is there any destruction without origin, and neither is destruction nor origination possible without what continues to be.”⁵

Reality of Categories/Substances

In the same way of triple formation theory, the Jainas described the reality of the world as many, changing, and possess infinite qualities. They uphold the existence of the world is absolutely founded on two categories, namely, Jiva or soul substance and Ajiva or non-soul substance, which are regarded as separate and independent realities. For them, each and every object of the world possesses innumerable positive and negative characters. They argue that the entire universe is composed of six substances of matter, space, time, motion and rest together with the soul. Among these substances, time is regarded as non-extended or *anastikaya*, others are known as extended or

astikaya dravyas. Because time does not extend like body in the space but the others do and, it should be noted that among the extended substances matter/*pudgala* alone has a form and all other substances are formless, even though they are extended substances. So, we can classify the whole infinite substances as dharmastikaya, adhrmastikaya and akasastikaya, they are known to us as *pudgala*, *jiva* and *kala* respectively (*dharmādharmākāśāstikāyāste*). Thus, the universe is divided into the two eternal, co-existing realities of *jiva*, the conscious spiritual substance and *ajiva*, the non-conscious substance. These classifications of substances of Jaina make it very clear that the universe cannot be describe either on the basis of the spirit alone or matter alone, or both spirit and matter. The multidimensional explanation of the universe demands to admit not only the reality of the spirit and the matter but also the other substances of space and time together with the substances of motion and rest as well.

According to them, there are innumerable material atoms and innumerable individual souls, and each atom and each soul possess innumerable aspects of its own. It is true to say that a thing has got an infinite number of characteristics of its own. In fact, as a finite being, it is impossible for us to know all the qualities of a thing and we can know only some qualities of some things. As far as our knowledge is necessarily relative and limited and so all our judgements are also limited. For them, on the one hand the change is true of the substance, whereas permanence is true in another respect as well. The problem of contradiction dissolves when we remember that each predication is relative and not absolute, as described by the syadvada. Thus, according to the Jainas a substance is real/*sat* and the Reality consists of three elements like, origination, permanence, and decay which characterizes the reality, or, are there in a substance. In so far as the essential characters of the ultimate substances are abiding, the world is permanent, and insofar as the accidental characters undergo modification, the world also changes. From this it is evident that, a substance which possess the factors of origination, permanence, and decay, is the fountain stone of the multiple nature of reality.

Conclusion

The concept of reality gets enriched in Jainism as it recommends

that the reality cannot be the one and ultimate, at the same time it can have a multi-dimensional form as well. Thus, the reality differed from individual to individual, that is, the reality of one individual may not be the reality for others. Anekantavada of Jainism proposes a form of synthesis and proposes that reality has many forms as seen by various individuals and we have to respect the reality perceived by everyone. The Jain states that truth and reality is complex in nature and always has multiple aspects. The fact is that we can experience the Reality, but it is not possible to express it completely with language. Thus, according to the Jainas a substance is real and the Reality consists of three factors such as origination, permanence and decay. Hence all the three elements such characterize reality are there in a substance.

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